

Thermodynamics of Hydration of Cellulose and Starch in the Absence and Presence of Neutral Salts

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Manuscript received 22 April 1993

Extents of hydration of different polysachharides such as cellulose, starch, carboxymethyl cellulose in the presence and absence of some inorganic electrolytes, sucrose and urea have been studied using isopiestic vapour pressure technique. The shapes of the water vapour adsorption isotherms for different polysachharides are in qualitative agreement with type III BET isotherm.

At the state of monolayer saturation, only a small fraction of water molecules are bound to the exposed surface of polysachharides. At water activity approaching unity, moles (Δn_1^0) of water bound per mole of glucose residues are 2.7, 2.9 and 40.3 for cellulose, starch and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) respectively. Standard free energy changes (ΔG^0) and enthalpy changes (ΔH^0) for three polysachharides in bringing water activity from zero to unity have been evaluated from the experimental data. From examination of these thermodynamic parameters, hydration of polysachharides has been found to be a spontaneous process controlled both by enthalpy and entropy effects. The excess hydration of the three polysachharides in the presence of several inorganic salts, urea and sucrose have been estimated from isopiestic experiments and free energies of excess hydration have been evaluated using integrated forms of the Gibbs adsorption equations. The absolute values of water and salt binding to these polysachharides have also been obtained from thermodynamic considerations.

Cellulose and starch are polysachharides which are formed in the plant systems by polymerisation of glucose. Study of extent of hydration of starch is extremely important in food science and role of water-cellulose interaction in plant growth, animal food digestion are highly important from biological standpoint. For this reason, attempts have been made by many workers¹⁻⁷ to study the water-polysachharide and water-glucose interactions using different physicochemical techniques.

For several years, the study of binding of water to powdered proteins⁸⁻¹⁴, nucleic acids¹⁵, surfactants and powdered solids¹⁶⁻¹⁸ both in the absence and presence of neutral salts have been investigated using isopiestic vapour pressure technique. The results of such study have been utilised for the evaluation of thermodynamic parameters related to water-biopolymer, water-surfactant and water-powdered solid interactions. Such study will now be extended to investigate the thermodynamic aspects of water-polysachharide interaction.

Results and Discussion

Cellulose, starch and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) are all polysachharides made up of monomeric glucose residues or their carboxymethyl derivatives. Cellulose is a fibrous, tough and water-insoluble unbranched homopolysachharide of 10000 or more D-glucose units connected by 1-4 glucosidic bonds. These 1-4 linkages occur in β -configuration¹⁹ as a result of which D-glucose chains assume an extended conformation and undergo side-by-side aggregation into insoluble fibrils. Linear chains of cellulose in the fibrils are held together by crosslinks of large number of hydrogen bonds¹⁹. Each nonionic glucose residue in the chain contains three free hydroxyl groups which may mostly involve in interchain hydrogen bond formation but few hydroxyl groups may combine with external water molecules as a result of polymer hydration. Carboxymethyl cellulose in higher pH becomes sodium salt of polyelectrolyte. It is highly soluble in water when poly-ion assumes random-coiled conformation

Fig 1 Plots of n_1^a vs a_1 for cellulose at (●) 30° and (○) 37°

Starch obtained from rice is a mixture of polysaccharides α -amylose and amylopectin, both of which are made of glucose residues. α -Amylose consists of long, unbranched chains of D-glucose units¹⁹ connected by $\alpha(1-4)$ linkages in contrast to cellulose where the linkage is $\beta(1-4)$. The glycosidic linkages joining successive glucose residues in amylopectin are $\alpha(1-4)$ but there exist branch points in this branched polymer thus forming $\alpha(1-6)$ linkages between glucose residues¹⁹. The $\alpha(1-4)$ linkages of amylose and amylopectin cause the chain to assume tightly coiled helix structure¹⁹ in which many hydroxyl groups are in intra-chain hydrogen bonding interaction with each other whereas far off groups remaining in the outer region of the helix may involve in the process of hydration in contact with bulk water. The fraction of branches in glucose residues in starch is usually low¹⁹ compared to linear polymerisation of glucose.

cellulose (CMC) are presented at different temperatures. The shapes of all these isotherms resemble type III BET isotherm. The BET equation²⁰ in linear form reads,

$$\frac{a_1}{n_1^a (1 - a_1)} = \frac{1}{n_m K_B} + \frac{K_B - 1}{n_m K_B} a_1 \quad (1)$$

Fig 2 Plots of n_1^a vs a_1 for starch at (●) 30° and (○) 37°

In Figs. 1-3, the isotherms for water-vapour adsorption by cellulose, starch and carboxymethyl

Fig. 3. Plots n_1^a vs a_1 for carboxymethyl cellulose at (●) 23° and (○) 37°.

The BET plot of $a_1/n_1^a(1-a_1)$ against a_1 is found to be linear in the range of P/P_0 equal to 0–0.75 in all cases. According to Pauling²¹, n_m stands for moles of H₂O strongly bound to free hydrophilic groups present per kg of polysaccharide (or per mole of glucose residue) thus forming primary layer of hydration of biopolymer. Also K_B is equal to $\exp(Q_m/RT)$, where Q_m is the heat of adsorption in this primary state of hydration. In Table 1, values of n_m and Q_m for different polysaccharides are presented in appropriate units. Thus respective mole of water strongly bound to the hydroxyl groups of glucose residue is only 0.16 and 0.21 for cellulose and starch even though three hydroxyl groups per residue are present. This means that only one hydroxyl group per six or five residues of cellulose remains strongly hydrated since rest of hydroxyl groups are involved in inter-chain and

intra-chain hydrogen bonding interactions. In the case of CMC, however, many of these hydrogen bonds are broken due to electrostatic repulsion between –COO groups in the chain so that 4.5 moles of H₂O become strongly bound to one mole of monomeric glucose derivative.

BET equation does not hold good in all these systems when a_1 is above 0.75. Here n_1^a rises sharply with a_1 until at unit water activity, extrapolated value of n_1^a equal to Δn_1^0 can be evaluated¹². Values of Δn_1^0 for different polysaccharides are presented in Table 1.

At 37°, one finds that nearly 3 moles of water are associated per mole of glucose unit in cellulose as well as in starch both having three free hydroxyl groups per glucose residue. For cross-linked

TABLE 1— VALUES OF n_m , Q_m and Δn_1^0 FOR HYDRATION OF POLYSACCHARIDES

Sample	temp °C	n_m		Q_m		Δn_1^0	
		Moles of H ₂ O/ mole of residue	Moles of H ₂ O/ kg of polysachharide	kJ mol ⁻¹ of residue	kJ kg ⁻¹ of polysachha- ride	Moles of H ₂ O/ mole of residue	Moles of water/ kg of poly- sachharide
Cellulose	30	0.15	0.97	140	863	2.05	12.7
Cellulose	37	0.16	1.02	63.5	391	2.7	16.7
Starch	30	0.23	1.43	86.8	535	2.94	18.2
Starch	37	0.21	1.33	86	530	2.94	18.2
Carboxy- methyl cellulose	23	0.7	2.89	50.4	207	27.9	115
Carboxy- methyl cellulose	37	0.67	2.77	58.4	240	40.3	166

amylopectin, free hydroxyl groups of the residue are however two. It appears that one free hydroxyl group of polymer at P/P_0 equal to unity, is associated with one H₂O group by hydrogen bonding interaction. In the case of CMC, under this situation, 40 moles of H₂O are in association per mole of hydrophilic group (i.e. COOH and OH group) per glucose residue at 37°. These large number of H₂O molecules may become associated with each other close to the primary hydration sites thus forming multilayers. Values of Δn_1^0 for cellulose and CMC are also observed to decrease with decrease of temperature as a result of hydrophobic effect²². Such effect of temperature is observed to be absent in starch (vide Table 1).

From the analysis of the slopes of the curve, obtained from the plot of a_1 vs n_1^a , one will find that the activity gradient¹² dn_1^a/da_1 for each curve initially increases with increase of n_1^a until it reaches a maximum value beyond which the gradient decreases gradually with further increase of a_1 . The value of the gradient approaches zero, when n_1^a becomes equal to Δn_1^0 . As mentioned earlier⁸, this behaviour of activity gradient may indicate that different water molecules present in the bound phase of polysachharide are in interaction with different water-binding sites with varied degrees of free energies. Only at and above unit water activity, the free energy of water remaining free becomes equal to that of bulk water²³. The free energy change ΔG_w for binding water to polysachharide

due to the change of water activity from zero to its standard state of unit activity can be calculated by using equation (2) of Bull²³,

$$\Delta G_w = -RT \int_0^{a_1=1} \frac{n_1^a}{a_1} da_1 \quad (2)$$

The area generated from the plot of n_1^a/a_1 against a_1 between limits a_1 equal to zero and 1, has been graphically estimated so that the values of standard free energies of hydration of cellulose, starch and CMC have been evaluated at different temperatures. These values (Table 2) are all negative which means that hydration of all types of polysachharides considered here is a spontaneous process. The value of $-\Delta G_w^0$ at 37° (Table 2) is found to be highest for CMC because this polysachharide contains at least one ionic group per residue of glucose derivative, as a result of which the polysachharide dissolves in water to a significant extent. Value of the free energy decrease is found to be lowest for cellulose, so that cellulose remains in insoluble state in presence of water at a_1 equal to unity. Value of $-\Delta G_w^0$ for starch is considerably higher than that of cellulose. The affinity of the water for interaction with polysachharide in presence of $\alpha(1-4)$ and $\beta(1-4)$ linkage is found to be widely different. This means that due to its affinity towards water, starch can be dispersed in aqueous phase as hydrophilic colloidal particles. Dependence of the values of $-\Delta G_w^0$ on temperature for starch and cellulose is not significant also (vide Table 1) whereas this is significant in the case of CMC.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF Δn_1^0 , STANDARD FREE ENERGY, ENTHALPY AND ENTROPY CHANGES FOR DEHYDRATION OF POLYSACCHARIDES

Sample	Average temp. °C	Δn_1^0 (moles of water/kg of polysaccharides)	Δn_1^0 (moles of water/mole of polysaccharides)	$-\Delta G_{w(av)}^0$ kJ kg ⁻¹ of polysaccharides	ΔH_{av}^0 kJ kg ⁻¹ of polysaccharides	ΔH_{int}^0 kJ kg ⁻¹ of polysaccharides	$T_{av}\Delta S_{w(av)}^0$ kJ kg ⁻¹ of polysaccharides	$\Delta S_{w(av)}^0$ kJ K ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ of polysaccharides
Cellulose	37	16.7	2.7	8.0	-29.5	-625	-616	-2.01
Cellulose	30	12.7	2.05	8.5				
Starch	37	18.2	2.94	13.7	38.9	367	380	1.24
Starch	30	18.2	2.94	12.5				
Carboxy-methyl cellulose	37	166	40.3	33	249	1103	1073	3.51
Carboxy-methyl cellulose	23	115	27.9	268				

The integral enthalpy (ΔH_{int}) for water vapour adsorption by polysaccharides can be calculated from the Hill equation^{10,23} (3) based on the validity of Clausius-Clapeyron relation,

$$\Delta H_{int} = -R \int_0^{\Delta n_1^0} \frac{T_1 T_2}{T_2 - T_1} \ln \frac{a_1^I}{a_1^a} d n_1^a \quad (3)$$

where a_1^I and a_1^a are water activities at temperatures T_2 and T_1 respectively. The term in the right-side of equation (3) for a particular value of n_1^a can be calculated from the experimental data. From the area obtained from the plot of this calculated value against n_1^a , between the limits zero and Δn_1^0 , the integral enthalpy for hydration for different polysaccharides at average temperature T_{av} [equal to $1/2 (T_1 + T_2)$] have been evaluated. The value of $(\Delta G_w)_{av}$ at temperature T_{av} may be taken as $1/2 [(\Delta G_w)T_1 + (\Delta G_w)T_2]$ so that its value can also be estimated from the data presented in Table 2. The average values of $T_{av}\Delta S_{av}$ (ΔS_{av} being the average entropy of hydration) equal to $\Delta H_{int} - \Delta G_{av}$ for different polysaccharides are also presented in Table 2. One finds that in all cases, ΔH_{int} is close to $T_{av}\Delta S_{av}$ so that magnitudes of both entropy and enthalpy effects control the hydration process with nearly equal contributions. The signs of ΔH_{int}^0 and $T_{av}\Delta S_{av}^0$ may be positive or negative but ΔG_{av}^0 is always negative for polysaccharide hydration.

In Figs. 4–10, values of excess binding of solute

Fig. 4. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs n_2/n_1 for starch in presence of different solutes at 37° : (○) KBr, (Δ) KI and (●) KCl.

to polysaccharides in the presence of water have been plotted against n_2/n_1 (or $m_2/55.5$). The solutes used are LiCl, NaCl, KCl, KBr, KI, Na₂SO₄, urea and CaCl₂. We find with interest that at lower values of n_2/n_1 the solute excess is positive but at higher values of n_2/n_1 (or $m_2/55.5$) the solute excess becomes negative. According to the concept of the relative excesses, the excess of water Γ_2^1 becomes negative when Γ_1^2 is positive and vice

Fig. 5. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs n_2/n_1 for starch in presence of different solutes at 37° : (○) LiCl and (Δ) NaCl.

versa. Γ_1^2 is defined by the equation,

$$\Gamma_1^2 = n_1^t - n_2^t \left(\frac{n_1}{n_2} \right) \quad (4)$$

Fig. 7. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs n_2/n_1 for cellulose in presence of different solutes at 37° : (○) sucrose, (Δ) KCl and (●) KBr.

Fig. 6. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs n_2/n_1 for starch in presence of different solutes at 37° : (m) Na_2SO_4 [II, II], (Δ) urea [I, I] and (●) CaCl_2 [II, II].

After combination with equation (12) it will assume the form,

$$\Gamma_1^2 = -\Gamma_2^1 \frac{n_1}{n_2} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 8. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs n_2/n_1 for cellulose in presence of different solutes at 37° : (○) KI and (Δ) urea.

Fig. 9. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs n_2/n_1 for cellulose in presence of different solutes at 37° : (○) CaCl₂ [II, I], (Δ) Na₂SO₄ [II, I], (⊙) NaCl [I, I] and (●) LiCl [I, I].

From the known values of Γ_2^1 and n_1/n_2 (equal to $55.5/m_2$), the values of Γ_1^2 which become fixed can be directly calculated. Thus when Γ_2^1 is negative, value of Γ_1^2 becomes positive and vice versa¹⁴. For most solutes, we find a point in each isotherm when Γ_2^1 or Γ_1^2 becomes zero at a particular value of m_2 . The composition of the bulk and surface phases become identical at this solute concentration (azeotropic state). Different values of m_2 (equal to m_2') at azeotropic points²³ are reported in Table 3.

Now n_1^t and n_2^t may be written as

$$n_1^t = n_1 + \Delta n_1 \quad (6)$$

$$n_2^t = n_2 + \Delta n_2 \quad (7)$$

where Δn_1 and Δn_2 are moles of solvent and solute components respectively per kg (or per mole of residue) of polysaccharide and n_1 and n_2 are amounts of these compounds remaining in the unbound or free state. Inserting these relations in equations (12) and (4), one obtains relations (8) and (9),

Fig. 10. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs n_2/n_1 for carboxymethyl cellulose in presence of salts at 37° : (○) NaCl [I, I] and (Δ) urea [II, II].

$$\Gamma_1^2 = \Delta n_1 - \Delta n_2 \frac{n_1}{n_2} \quad (8)$$

and

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \Delta n_2 - \Delta n_1 \frac{n_2}{n_1} \quad (9)$$

From these two equations it is clear that Γ_2^1 (or Γ_1^2) contains both Δn_1 and Δn_2 terms. In the absence of another independent equation, values of Δn_1 and Δn_2 cannot be obtained unless the plot of Γ_2^1 against n_2/n_1 becomes linear¹⁴. From the linear regions of the plots in Figs. 4–10, the values of Δn_1 and Δn_2 have been evaluated. These are presented in Table 3.

Values of Δn_1 for cellulose stands in the order : NaCl > Na₂SO₄ > Urea > LiCl \approx KCl > KI < KBr \approx CaCl₂, whereas that order for starch is Na₂SO₄ > NaCl > KCl > LiCl > Sucrose > Urea > KBr. One also finds with interest that for NaCl and urea, Δn_1 in all three polysaccharides are high and their magnitudes are comparable. Also comparison of data in Table 1 indicates that mole of H₂O bound per mole of residue increases ten times or more in the presence of salts, sucrose

TABLE 3—AZEOTROPIC POINTS, Δn_1 , Δn_2 for POLYSACCHARIDES IN PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT SOLUTES AT 37°

Sample	Solute	m_2 at azeotropic point	Δn_1		Δn_2		ΔG°_{ws}	
			Moles of water/kg of polysachharides	Moles of water/mole of polysachharides	Moles of solute/kg of polysachharides	Moles of solute/mole of polysachharids	kJ kg ⁻¹ of polysachharides	kJ mol ⁻¹ of polysachharides
Strach	KBr	0.045	50	8.1	2.02	0.327	53.5	8.67
	KI	0.038	60	9.72	2.25	0.364	9	1.45
	KCl	0.032	62.5	10.1	2	0.324	67	10.8
	LiCl	0.035	62.5	10.1	2.25	0.364	7.5	1.21
	NaCl	0.032	83.3	13.5	2.65	0.429	52	8.42
	Na ₂ SO ₄	0.018	80	12.9	1.46	0.236	150	24.3
	Urea	—	80	12.9	1.26	0.204	—	—
	CaCl ₂	0.033	50	8.1	1.69	0.273	53	8.58
Cellulose	Sucrose	0.019	70	11.3	1.35	0.218	—	—
	KCl	0.031	87.5	14.1	2.6	0.421	78	12.6
	KBr	0.049	50	8.1	2.5	0.405	22	3.56
	KI	0.043	66.6	10.7	3	0.486	7	1.13
	Urea	—	60	9.72	6.6	1.06	—	—
	CaCl ₂	0.026	—	—	—	—	49	7.94
	Na ₂ SO ₄	0.025	133.3	21.6	3.25	0.526	152	24.6
	NaCl	0.053	100	16.2	5.75	0.931	(-) 2 × 10 ⁻³	(-) 0.324 × 10 ⁻³
	LiCl	0.037	75	12.1	2.75	0.445	19	3.07
Carboxy-methyl cellulose	NaCl	0.032	100	24.3	3.55	0.863	68	16.5
	Urea	0.079	88.8	21.6	9.1	1.72	—	—

and urea. Here water molecules must have formed polymolecular layers around polysachharides. There also occurs small but significant amount of salt and solute binding to residues as expected from other studies⁷. At azeotropic point $\Gamma_2^1 = 0$ so that n_2/n_1 becomes equal to $\Delta n_2/\Delta n_1$.

The apparent standard free energy change ΔG°_{ap} for binding Γ_2^m moles of electrolyte in bringing the bulk concentration from zero to unity hypothetically in mole fraction scale can be obtained from the Gibbs equation (10) in integrated form²⁴,

$$\Delta G^{\circ}_{ap} = -RT(v_+ + v_-) \int_0^{X_{\pm}} \frac{\Gamma_2^1}{f_{\pm} X_{\pm}} d(f_{\pm} X_{\pm}) + \Gamma_2^m \ln \frac{1}{f_{\pm} X_{\pm}^m} \quad (10)$$

where v_+ and v_- are number of cations and anions obtained from the complete dissociation of an electrolyte. Also X_+ and f_{\pm} are mean mole fraction and mean activity coefficient of the salt at a given

state in bulk. Their values can be obtained from the known bulk molality m_2 and m_2 in solution. At each value of m_2 , we shall apparently assume $\Gamma_2^m = \Gamma_2^1$ and $X_{\pm} = X_{\pm}^m$ so that value of ΔG°_{ap} for this state can be evaluated using equation (10). This value of ΔG°_{ap} is the apparent standard free energy change for salt polymer interaction since its value varies with increase of X_{\pm} . From the empirical plot of ΔG°_{ap} against $1/\sqrt{X_{\pm}}$, the value of the real actual standard free energy change ΔG° can be evaluated from linear extrapolation of the plot at X_{\pm} equal to unity. Maximum values of Γ_2^1 (i.e. Γ_2^m) have similarly been evaluated using the linear extrapolation of the plot of Γ_2^1 versus $1/\sqrt{X_{\pm}}$ at X_{\pm} equal to unity. Values of ΔG° and Γ_2^m for different solutes are presented in Table 3. Different electrolytes in Table 3 stands in the following order in terms of ΔG° of starch : Na₂SO₄ > KCl > KBr ≈ CaCl₂ > NaCl > KI > LiCl, but in case of cellulose the

order is $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{KCl} > \text{CaCl}_2 > \text{KBr} > \text{LiCl} > \text{KI} > \text{NaCl}$.

In both the cases series does not bear any relation with lyotropic series.

Experimental

Powdered starch and cellulose were supplied by Centre for Biochemicals, CSIR, New Delhi. Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) used was supplied by Sigma. NaCl, KCl, Na_2SO_4 , CaCl_2 , KBr, KI, urea and sucrose were all of analytical grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout the study.

Starch, cellulose and carboxymethyl cellulose were dehydrated by keeping the samples in a desiccator containing H_2SO_4 for 5 days and then stored in another desiccator containing CaCl_2 . The average molecular weights of glucose residues in starch (neglecting contribution of 1-6 link) and cellulose were 162, so 1 kg of these samples always contains 6.17 moles of the monosachharide residue. In carboxymethyl cellulose²⁵, one or more hydroxyl groups are replaced by $-\text{CH}_2\text{COONa}$, so that the average molecular weight of the monomeric organic ion may be taken as 242. One kg of CMC thus contains 4.13 moles of unit of glucose derivative.

Following the isopiestic method originally used by Bull and Breese^{26,27}, moles of H_2O (n_1^a) adsorbed by 1 kg of polysachharides (or by 1 mole of glucose residue) were determined at different relative humidities P/P_0 . In this method, a definite weight of the dehydrated polymer was taken in a sample bottle. After weighing the bottle, its lid was taken out and the bottle was floated on H_2SO_4 solution taken in a desiccator which was then evacuated. The H_2SO_4 solution in the desiccator (called as reference solution) was frequently stirred for 5 days until state of isopiestic equilibrium between hydrated carbohydrate in the sample bottle and the H_2SO_4 solution in the reference was reached. The sample bottle with hydrated carbohydrate was taken out and weighed whereby value of n_1^a was estimated. The concentration of the H_2SO_4 was also determined and corresponding value of P/P_0 at this concentration

was obtained using standard table²⁸. According to Raoult's law, P/P_0 stands for the activity a_1 of water in the reference solution. The method has been described elsewhere in detail⁸.

For the determination of excess hydration^{11,14,16} of the polysachharides, a definite weight of the polymer along with a definite weight of the dry salt or urea was taken as sample in the weighing bottle. This was then floated on the reference solution taken in desiccator as before. The solution in the reference was made of same neutral salt or urea as that used in the sample bottle. The sample was brought in isopiestic equilibrium with the reference solution within 5 days. The sample bottle was taken out and weighed when total moles n_1^t of water in the sample was obtained. Total moles n_2^t of salt present in the sample were also known so that total molality (m_2^t) of the solute before any interaction with water and polymer are known. The polysachharide may bind water and solute so that molality of free solute dissolved in free water in the sample was different from m_2^t .

As pointed out before¹³, the molality m_2 of the solute in the reference solution at isopiestic equilibrium had been estimated by direct weighing of the solute obtained from the drying of a definite weight of the solution at 105–110°. For urea, LiCl, CaCl_2 and KI, indirect methods were used to determine m_2 , since these solutes may partly decompose at high temperature. These have been reported in detail earlier¹⁴.

Moles of solute (Γ_2^t) adsorbed from solution in the sample in contact with 1 kg of sample (or 1 mole of monomer residue) can be calculated using the relation¹⁴

$$\Gamma_2^t = \frac{18 n_1^t}{1000} (m_2^t - m_2) \quad (11)$$

where m_2^t is equal to $\frac{1000}{18} \frac{n_2^t}{n_1^t}$ so that its value can be calculated from the values of n_1^t and n_2^t obtained from the experiments. The molality m_2 of the free solute remaining dissolved

in free water in the sample in contact with 1 kg of polysachharide (or 1 mole of residue) may be taken to be equal to m_2 after neglecting the small contribution of the hydrated polysachharide to the vapour pressure. The reason for such neglect for powdered substances under these conditions have been discussed elsewhere¹³. Also m_2 is equal to $\frac{1000}{18} \frac{n_2}{n_1}$ where, n_1 and n_2 are moles of water and solute components respectively, present in free states per unit quantity of polysachharide. Inserting these values for m_2^t and m_2 in equation (11) we find

$$\Gamma_2^1 = n_2^t - n_1^t \frac{n_2}{n_1} \quad (12)$$

Γ_2^1 is thus identical as the Gibbs excess of solute bound per kg of sugar (or per mole of residue) of the polymer^{14,16}. Its value can also be directly calculated from the measured values of n_1^t , n_2^t and n_2/n_1 (equal to $m_2/55.5$) respectively.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P B) is grateful to UGC, New Delhi for the award of a Research Fellowship.

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